

Molluscan alien species in Galicia: new records and new data

Especies no-indígenas de moluscos en Galicia: nuevas citas y nuevos datos

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ABSTRACT

Although it is well known that Galicia has been a hotspot for the arrival of exotic marine mollusc species from other continents for decades, previously undetected new species continue to appear, associated with the bivalve aquaculture trade. While most of the species that have appeared are marine, freshwater and terrestrial species have also been found in recent years. Freshwater species all originate from the American continent and their arrival in our country seems to be linked to the aquarium trade. As for terrestrial species, although to a lesser extent, a potentially very dangerous pathway of introduction has been detected: the trade of ornamental plants, through which it is very easy to spread different species over a large area in a very short period, with the risk of future potential invaders. This paper addresses a total of 11 species, seven marine, three freshwater and one terrestrial. Our material of *Ocenebrellus inornatus* (Récluz, 1851), *Ferrissia californica* (Rowell, 1863) *Succinea costaricana* E. von Martens, 1898 constitutes first record in Galicia. One species is tentatively identified as the West African *Loripinus* cf. *senegalensis* (Cosel, 2005) which would also be a first record, and *Mercenaria mercenaria* (Linnaeus, 1758) is confirmed as an established species in the northern Iberian Peninsula. For the remaining six species already known in our area, data are updated and additional information deemed of interest is included.

RESUMEN

Si bien es bien sabido que Galicia ha sido un foco de llegada de especies exóticas de moluscos marinos procedentes de otros continentes durante décadas, siguen apareciendo nuevas especies no detectadas previamente, asociadas al comercio de bivalvos en acuicul-

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tura. Aunque la mayoría de las especies que han aparecido son marinas, en los últimos años también se han encontrado especies de agua dulce y terrestres. Todas las especies de agua dulce son originarias del continente americano y su llegada a nuestro país parece estar vinculada al comercio de acuariofilia. En cuanto a las especies terrestres, aunque en menor medida, se ha detectado una vía de introducción potencialmente muy peligrosa: el comercio de plantas ornamentales, a través del cual es muy fácil propagar diferentes especies en una amplia zona en un período muy corto, con el riesgo de futuros invasores potenciales. Este artículo aborda un total de 11 especies, siete marinas, tres de agua dulce y una terrestre. Nuestro material de *Ocenebrellus inornatus* (Récluz, 1851), *Ferrissia californica* (Rowell, 1863) y *Succinea costaricana* (E. von Martens, 1898) constituye la primera cita en Galicia. Una especie se identifica provisionalmente como *Loripinus* cf. *senegalensis* (Cosel, 2005), de África occidental, lo que también constituiría una primera cita, y *Mercenaria mercenaria* (Linnaeus, 1758) se confirma como especie establecida en el norte de la Península Ibérica. Para las seis especies restantes ya conocidas en nuestra área, se actualizan los datos y se incluye información adicional considerada de interés.

KEYWORDS: Marine molluscs, freshwater molluscs, land snails, alien species, new records, Galicia.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Moluscos marinos, moluscos dulceacuícolas, moluscos de tierra, especies exóticas, nuevas citas, Galicia.

INTRODUCTION

Activities related to the aquaculture sector have a long history in Galicia, where they have been developed successfully thanks to the extraordinarily favourable natural conditions with the contribution of deep and cold waters loaded with nutrients that emerge on our coasts. This phenomenon, known as upwelling, makes conditions extremely favourable for the farming of different species belonging to different phyla of marine vertebrates and invertebrates.

It was not until the early 1980s that aquaculture started with species other than the mussel, *Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lamarck, 1819. Specifically, the common oyster, *Ostrea edulis* Linnaeus, 1758 and the Japanese oyster, *Magallana gigas* (Thunberg, 1793) were species declared cultivable, but due to the lack of native breeding with which to begin the farming process, it was decided to import spat from countries such as Italy, France and the United Kingdom. The inadequate cleaning of the imported seed led to finding the spawn, juveniles and adults of exotic marine invertebrates in Galicia (ROLÁN ET AL., 1985), where some of them have adapted and

naturalized perfectly. Such species as *Bolinus brandaris* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Hexaplex trunculus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Steromphala albida* (Gmelin, 1791) or *Pseudofusus rostratus* (Olivi, 1792) began to appear in Arousa, but there was doubt about whether some of them had arrived naturally, slowly advancing along the Atlantic coast of the Iberian Peninsula or only through imported oyster farming materials.

However, there was no doubt that species originating from other continents had previously appeared in parts of northern Europe, such as *Crepidula fornicata* (Linnaeus, 1758), or in very specific parts of the Mediterranean, such as *Anadara kagoshimensis* (Tokunaga, 1906). This work focuses on species, which have continued arriving in connection with aquaculture, some of them exhibiting invasive behaviour. Their spread into our waters poses a risk, especially considering that Galicia is a European powerhouse in the exploitation and commercialisation of bivalves for human consumption.

Reviewing the appearance of foreign species in Galicia, the first identified, in

the early 1980s was *Crepidula fornicata* in the Aldán cove, Ría de Pontevedra (ROLÁN, 1983). It was followed shortly afterwards by *Anadara kagoshimensis*, found alive among oyster seed from Italy (ROLÁN ET AL., 1985, as *Scapharca cornea*) in the Ría de Arousa, and later *Crepidatella dilatata* (Lamarck, 1822) again in the Aldán cove (ROLÁN & HORRO, 2005). Subsequently, *Xenostrobus securis* (Lamarck, 1819) in the Ría de Vigo (GARCÍA ET AL., 2006), and finally, *Rapana venosa* (Valenciennes, 1846) (ROLÁN & BAÑÓN, 2007), *Mya arenaria* Linnaeus, 1758 (ROLÁN & ACUÑA, 2008) and *Anadara transversa* (Say, 1822) (TRIGO, 2012) in the Ría de Arousa.

Currently, and despite the fact that seed import conditions have dramatically changed, new exotic species continue to arrive and successfully naturalize in our waters. Although most of them are attributable to human activities related to aquaculture, there are some species whose arrival in our waters can only be explained by maritime traffic in any of its facets and originating from places, sometimes far away, whose intermediate or final destination is a Galician port.

This is not just about mollusc species, algae such as *Rugulopteryx okamurae* (E.Y. Dawson) I.K. Hwang, W.J. Lee & H.S. Kim, 2009 from the Northwest Pacific, or even flatworms such as *Postenterogonia orbicularis* (Schmarda, 1859) native to New Zealand, arrived to our shores, posing a significant danger for the bivalve aquaculture industry.

There is no area that can be spared from the arrival of alien species, and freshwater species have also been detected in Galicia, being their entry linked to the aquarium trade. So far, only *Potamopyrgus antipodarum* (J. E. Gray, 1843), *Ferrissia californica* (Rowell, 1863), *Corbicula fluminea* (O.F.Müller, 1774) and *Pseudosuccinea columella* (Say, 1817) have been recorded, but some more have now been found, opening up a field that still requires much more sampling and verification to check for undetected species

Terrestrial species are not exempt either, as they disperse very easily through the ever-growing trade of ornamental plants, in which plants from different continents are moved to others without considering the species of molluscs that may accompany them, or their eggs which are typically buried in the substrate. Once they reach their destination country, they randomly disperse from arrival warehouses to thousands of nurseries scattered throughout the country. It is also a new field in which much remains to be sampled and tested.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The marine specimens obtained have been collected in regular samplings along the coasts of Galicia (Fig. 1). This work is supported by the data provided through specimens found by fishermen and hobbyists who have freely collaborated (Citizen Science). These samplings are normally carried out by walking along the intertidal zone of the Galician coast, also including inspection of local fishing gear from small fishing ports, and scuba dives down to 30 meters deep.

Much more recently, sampling began to be carried out in freshwater streams. In this case, rivers on the southern side of the Ría de Vigo have been surveyed, but all Galician rivers must be examined to determine whether the newly identified species, or others still unpredicted, are present.

In the case of terrestrial species, only one has been found so far, but several samples need to be taken at different points across Galicia to determine if more species from outside have arrived. In this case, it will be necessary to establish a specific sampling method that has not yet been implemented.

Photographs of the whole specimens were taken with a Canon EOS 550D digital camera for the largest specimens and for the smallest, an Olympus SZX 12 trinocular and camera Olympus SC 180, with image stacking using the Automontage software.

RESULTS

Class GASTROPODA
Order LITTORINIMORPHA
Family CALYPTRAEIDAE

Crepipatella dilatata (Lamarck, 1822) (Fig. 2)

Material examined: GALICIA • 2 specimens; A Coruña, Malpica, Malpica deck; 43°19'22.70"N, 8°48'32.65"W; 30 Dec. 2022 • 2 specimens; A Coruña, Carnota, Caldebarcos, Carnota Beach; 42°50'31.81"N, 9°06'29.89"W; 23 Aug. 2023; J. E. Trigo leg. • 5 specimens; A Coruña, Carnota, Lariño Beach; 42°46'15.25"N, 9°07'17.50"W; 23 Aug. 2023; J. E. Trigo leg. • 14 specimens; A Coruña, Noia, Testal Beach; 42°47'28.48"N, 8°54'42.76"W; 7 Aug. 2023; J.E. Trigo leg. • 5 specimens; A Coruña, Aguiño, Da Tasca Beach; 42°31'21.18"N, 8°54'42.76"W; 12 May 2019; J. E. Trigo leg. • 17 specimens; A Coruña, Aguiño, Robalo Beach; 42°31'22.86"N, 9°00'59.62"W; 12 May 2019; J. E. Trigo leg. • 23 specimens; A Coruña, Ribeira, Coroso Beach; 42°34'09.32"N, 8°58'50.13"W; 23 Jul. 2019; J. E. Trigo leg. • 21 specimens; A Coruña, Boiro, Carragueiros beach; 42°36'48.68"N 8°52'30.20"W; 27 Nov. 2024; J. E. Trigo leg. • 14 specimens; A Coruña, Boiro, Mañóns beach; 42°37'50.72"N 8°51'04.58"W; 27 Nov. 2024; J.E. Trigo leg. • 76 specimens; Pontevedra, Arousa Island, Xastelas Beach; 42°31'52.31"N, 8°52'07.76"W; 22 Jun. 2019; J.E. Trigo leg. • 48 specimens; same data as for preceding; 18 Jul 2019; J.E. Trigo leg. • 96 specimens; same data as for preceding; 5 Jan. 2020; J.E. Trigo, J. Fernández and J. Pérez leg. • 53 specimens; same data as for preceding; 19 Feb. 2020; J.E. Trigo, and J. Fernández leg. • 85 specimens; same data as for preceding; 25 May 2021; J.E. Trigo, and J. Fernández leg. • 51 specimens; same data as for preceding; 5 Nov. 2021; J.E. Trigo, and J. Fernández leg. • 82 specimens; same data as for preceding; 5 Jun 2023; J.E. Trigo, and J. Fernández leg. • 35 specimens; Pontevedra, Cambados, Tragove; 42°31'17.62"N, 8°49'40.30"W; 8 Jan. 2012. J.E. Trigo leg. • 52 specimens; Same data as for preceding; 7 Dec. 2017; Juan E. Trigo leg. • 14 specimens; Pontevedra, O Grove, Fishing harbour; 42°29'51.50"N, 8°51'42.56"W; 12 Mar. 2009; J. E. Trigo leg. • 7 specimens; Pontevedra, Sanxenxo, Areas Beach; 42°23'37.64"N, 8°46'42.93"W; 31 Jul. 2020; J. E. Trigo leg. • 12 specimens; Pontevedra, Poio, Raxó Beach; 42°24'11.73"N, 8°45'13.50"W; 31 Jul. 2020; J. E. Trigo leg. • 6 specimens; Pontevedra, Bueu, Fishing harbour; 42°19'39.32"N, 8°47'04.82"W; 26 Oct. 2014; J. E. Trigo leg. • 13 specimens; Pontevedra, Aldán, Fishing harbour; 42°16'57.64"N, 8°49'20.20"W; 13 Apr. 2006; J. E. Trigo leg. • 13 specimens; same data as for preceding; 29 Nov. 2006; J. E. Trigo leg. • 3 specimens; same data as for preceding; 31 Jan. 2007; J. E. Trigo leg. • 3 specimens; Pontevedra, Aldán, Rabáns Beach; 42°17'57.15"N, 8°50'56.80"W; 14 Oct. 2024; J. E. Trigo leg. • 5 specimens; Pontevedra, Aldán, Area Brava Beach; 42°17'27.56"N, 8°50'22.34"W; 14 Oct. 2024; J. E. Trigo leg. • 29 specimens; Pontevedra, Cangas de Morrazo, Fishing harbour; 42°15'35.93"N, 8°46'59.14"W; 13 Apr. 2006; J. E. Trigo leg. • 4 specimens; same data as for preceding; 29 Nov. 2006; J. E. Trigo leg. • 3 specimens; Pontevedra, Cies Islands, San Martiño Island; 42°11'51.13"N, 8°53'34.59"W; 22 Oct. 2019; J. E. Trigo leg. • 3 specimens; Pontevedra, Nigrán, Playa América; 42°08'15.61"N, 8°49'14.70"W; 23 May 2018; Luis Rodríguez and Fernando Febrero leg. • 23 specimens; Pontevedra, Baiona, Concheiras Beach; 42°07'22.25"N, 8°51'06.60"W; 30 Jul. 2020; J. E. Trigo leg. • 7 specimens; Pontevedra, A Guarda, A Guarda deck; 41°53'54.97"N, 8°52'37.74"W; 9 Sep. 2018. J.E. Trigo leg.

Shell: Oval-rounded, convex with spirally enrolled apex. Concave septum with white S-shaped edge. Flat surface. Purplish brown interior. Exterior whitish to purplish brown with a white longitudinal line that is sometimes inconspicuous. Very variable in shape since it usually takes the shape of the substrate on which it is fixed.

Known distribution: From Brazil to the Strait of Magellan and the Falkland Islands in the Atlantic and the entire Chilean coast and part of Peru in the

Pacific (TRIGO *ET AL.*, 2018). In Europe it was cited for the first time in Galicia (ROLÁN & HORRO, 2005), later in Asturias (RICHTER, ARIAS & ANADÓN, 2012) and in the Ebro delta (LÓPEZ SORIANO & QUIÑONERO SALGADO, 2014).

Remarks: Very shortly after appearing in Galicia for the first time, this species began to appear in other places relatively distant from the first, such as Cangas de Morrazo in the Ría de Vigo and Santa Uxía de Ribeira, in the Ría de Arousa (ROLÁN & TRIGO, 2006, 2007) without any trace of

Figure 1. Situation of Galicia in Europe and main sampled sites of the species studied in this work.
Figura 1. Situación de Galicia en Europa y principales lugares muestreados de las especies objeto de estudio en este trabajo.

this species having appeared in previous samplings carried out in those areas, and later in Tragove, Cambados (TRIGO, 2012). In all these places, the common link is the companies dedicated to the purification of shellfish and bivalves for subsequent human consumption. There are official records of the entry of live Chilean mussels into Spain for 2004, 2007, 2008 and 2009 (MINISTERIO DE ECONOMÍA, COMERCIO Y EMPRESA, 2024) and this is the only possible way of introduction of this species on European coasts since there is no other official entry of any other molluscs or other live marine invertebrates from countries such as Chile or Argentina.

The invasive potential of this species is very worrying and can be seen in Figure 2A-D. The photographs taken in Tragove, Cambados, in 2011 and 2017 give an idea of its capacity to invade new spaces and displace all native marine invertebrate species that could usually be found on the rocks of the area (TRIGO, 2012). Although it was initially observed that the only ones capable of resisting *C. dilatata* were different species of barnacles, already in 2017, it was found that not even these were able to withstand the pressure, finding themselves completely relegated out of that zone.

Between the photos taken in 2017 and today there are no major changes regarding the area initially affected; only the occurrence of some green and brown algae, mainly *Ulva* spp and *Fucus* spp. These algae survive, leaving the rest covered with this exotic species which is capable of adhering in layers, being arranged one on top of the other, forming a conglomerate that leaves no gap for other species of invertebrates to settle. The only species of mollusc that has been observed coexisting with *C. dilatata*, curiously, is another exotic species, the gastropod *Steromphala adriatica* (R.A. Philippi, 1844), native to the Adriatic Sea and nat-

uralized in Galicia for almost two decades. This coexistence is not very well understood since the native species of the Trochidae family have completely disappeared from these occupied areas.

What raises concern is the extent of the areas affected by this species, which are expanding rapidly and thus, the first colony found in Aldán quickly moved into the interior of the Ría de Pontevedra (COLLIN, FARREL & CRAGG, 2009), where it can currently be found in the entire ría. The core of Cangas de Morrazo has been extending towards the interior of the Ría de Vigo, but also towards the Cíes Islands and the southern entrance of the same ría, all of it being affected. That colony of Ribeira has been extending towards the interior and exterior of the northern coast of the Ría de Arousa. The one in Cambados has been extending towards the southern part of the Isle of Arousa, towards O Grove and towards Vilagarcía de Arousa, so this ría is also completely affected. Ría de Muros, which has been colonized from Ría de Arousa, since no outbreaks were found as in other rías, has not been spared of this species and it is entirely affected, both on the north and south coasts, although at the moment, not with the same densities as in the rest of the rías. Currently, this species has been found as far as the town of Malpica, so its distribution area in Galicia extends from A Garda, on the border with Portugal to the north of Costa da Morte. In observations obtained from dives carried out at different points on the coast of Galicia, it has been proven that this species has colonized the entire strip between the intertidal zone and the 10 meter depth of the Rías Baixas.

It will be necessary to check over time if the Miño River, which in its last kilometres acts as a natural border between Portugal and Spain, is capable of acting as a barrier to this species towards the south.

(Right page) Figure 2. *Crepipatella dilatata*, Tragove, Cambados, Pontevedra. A-B: pictures taken in 2012. C-D: Pictures taken at the same place in 2017. E: Specimens covering inner and outer surface of a glass bottle in Ribeira marina, A Coruña. F: Specimens covering a section of plastic pipe. Arousa Island, Pontevedra.

Figura 2. *Crepipatella dilatata*, Tragove, Cambados, Pontevedra. A-B: Fotografías tomadas en 2012. C-D: Fotografías tomadas en el mismo lugar en 2017. E: Ejemplares cubriendo las partes interna y externa de una botella en el puerto deportivo de Ribeira, A Coruña. F: Ejemplares recubriendo una sección de tubería plástica. Illa de Arousa, Pontevedra.

Order NEOGASTROPODA

Family MURICIDAE

Ocenebrellus inornatus (Récluz, 1851) (Figs. 3, 4)

Material examined: GALICIA • 2 specimens; Pontevedra, Arousa Island, Xastelas Beach; 42°31'52.31"N, 8°52'07.76"W; 22 Jun. 2019; J.E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; same data as for preceding; 18 Jul 2019; J.E. Trigo leg. • 16 specimens; same data as for preceding; 5 Jan. 2020; J.E. Trigo, J. Fernández and J. Pérez leg. • 18 specimens; same data as for preceding; 19 Feb. 2020; J.E. Trigo, and J. Fernández leg. • 18 specimens; same data as for preceding; 25 May 2021; J.E. Trigo, and J. Fernández leg. • 58 specimens; same data as for preceding; 5 Nov. 2021; J.E. Trigo, and J. Fernández leg. • 152 specimens; same data as for preceding; 5 Jun 2023; J.E. Trigo, and J. Fernández leg.

Shell: Oval aperture with light brown operculum and a spiral formed by 6 or 7 whorls in profile at an almost right angle. The last whorl has normally prominent axial ridges at irregular intervals. Short, straight siphonal channel which may be open along its entire length. External lip thick, generally with wide border. Chalky texture, with colours varying from white to bluish grey and sometimes with chestnut brown bands. It can reach sizes up to 60 mm in length.

Animal: Very similar to that of *Ocenebra erinaceus* (Linnaeus, 1758), pale cream in colour with some darker spots distributed irregularly all over its body.

Known distribution: *Ocenebrellus inornatus* is native to the North Pacific, including northern China, Korea and Japan, up to the Sakhalin and Kuril Islands in Russia (Lützen et al, 2012; Babaran, 2017). The expansion of this gastropod across the American and European coasts is well known and perfectly documented. The first discovery outside its natural distribution area was on the west coast of the United States in 1924 (GALTSOFF, 1929), linked to the importation of *Magallana gigas* (Thunberg, 1793) from Japan and from where, in a few years, it was extended to all the states on the west coast of the United States and to British Columbia in Canada. In Europe, it was recorded for the first time in France in 1995 (DE MONTAUDOUIN & SAURIAU, 2000), and the introduction could have been due to the importation of *M. gigas* broodstock from British Columbia in the 1970s. It was

later cited in the coasts of the Netherlands (FAASSE & LIGTHART, 2007, 2009), Portugal (AFONSO, 2011) and Denmark (LÜTZEN ET AL., 2012), usually associated with the trade in *M. gigas*.

Ecology: The area in which the first living specimens were found is predominantly sandy in its highest area with scattered rocks, among which no live specimens of *O. inornatus* were found and only empty shells were found in the sand. Descending towards the lower intertidal zone, muddy sand predominates with some medium-sized rocks and stones. Here, the specimens found were established either under stones and rocks in a resting attitude or in a predatory attitude, tightly attached to different species of bivalves abundant in the area, making holes in their shells to feed on them. References found on the substrate or substrates that *O. inornatus* prefers in colonized areas in different parts of America and Europe have in common the oyster beds. These beds are naturally found between the intertidal zone and 5-6 meters deep. Reference is also made to the fact that they can be found in the middle part of the coastal zone and on rocky coasts (PIGEOT ET AL., 2000).

Regarding the species on which *O. inornatus* usually preys, it is known that this species prefers, at least in Europe, *O. edulis* over *M. gigas* and relatively small sizes (BABARAN, 2017). In addition to oysters such as *Ostrea lurida* P.P. Carpenter, 1864 and *M. gigas* in waters of the American Pacific or *O. edulis* and *M. gigas* in Europe, reference is also made to its intense predatory action on other

Figure 3. A-D: *Ocinebrellus inornatus*. E-H: *Ocenebra erinaceus*. I-N: different specimens of *O. inornatus* showing its morphological variability. All specimens found in Xastelas Beach, Arousa Island, Pontevedra.

Figura 3. A-D: *Ocinebrellus inornatus*. E-H: *Ocenebra erinaceus*. I-N: diferentes ejemplares de *O. inornatus* encontrados, mostrando su variabilidad morfológica. Todos los ejemplares encontrados en Playa de Xastelas, Illa de Arousa, Pontevedra.

commercial bivalves such as clams, other gastropods and barnacles (DUCKWALL, 2009) and on other species of oysters and mussels (Lützen et al., 2012). We have been able to verify this fact in our study area, where *O. inornatus* has been observed feeding on the commercial bivalve species *Ruditapes philippinarum* (A. Adams & Reeve, 1850), *Ruditapes decussatus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Polititapes aureus* (Gmelin, 1791), *Venerupis corrugata* (Gmelin, 1791),

Cerastoderma edule (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lamarck, 1819.

Within the range of sizes of the specimens under study and taking into account that this species can reach 27 mm in its first year of life (DUCKWALL, 2009) and that many of the specimens collected greatly exceed 45 mm, it can be inferred that, at the time the first live specimens were found, they had built a stable population in which specimens are at least 5 years old.

Figure 4. A: specimen of *Ocinebrellus inornatus* during the spawning in November 2021; B: egg capsules of *O. inornatus*; C: egg capsules of *O. erinaceus*; D: *O. inornatus* egg capsules, where the eggs inside can be seen through transparency; E: eggs extracted from the inside of a single capsule.
Figura 4. A: ejemplar de *O. inornatus* durante la puesta en noviembre de 2021; B: cápsulas ovígeras de *O. inornatus*; C: cápsulas ovígeras de *O. erinaceus*; D: cápsulas ovígeras de *O. inornatus* en donde pueden apreciarse por transparencia los huevos en su interior; E: huevos extraídos del interior de una sola cápsula.

The egg capsules are pale yellowish or cream in colour with a very particular shape, with folded edges and a protruding tip very similar to those of the native species *O. erinaceus* (Fig. 3). Inside each capsule, there are hundreds of white eggs (Fig. 4), which contrast with observations made in the Pacific where it is indicated that between 3 and 10 minia-

ture juveniles hatch from each clutch (QUAYLE 1969; HOUART & SIRENKO 2003).

Remarks: The expansion of this species across different European countries has led to suspect that *O. inornatus* could be found in Galicia, also because other exotic species that had previously been cited in France, Italy or the United Kingdom (from where practically all of

the seed of different commercial bivalves is imported for fattening in Galician rafts or for cultivation in sandy areas), were later found in Galicia.

Our material should be the first record for Spanish waters, but unfortu-

nately, the species was reported by Bañón, Fariña & De Carlos (2023) based on our indications; we profoundly regret that this discovery has been published without taking into account the initial collectors.

Subclass HETEROBRANCHIA

Family LYMNAEIDAE

Pseudosuccinea columella (Say, 1817) (Fig. 5A, B)

Material examined: GALICIA • 4 specimens; Pontevedra, Nigrán, Muíños River; 42°08'00.57"N, 08°48'39.84"W; 3 Oct. 2023; J.E. Trigo, L. Rodríguez & F. Febrero leg. • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, Baiona, Miñor River; 42°06'39.89"N, 08°46'17.08"W; 30 Sep. 2024; Juan E. Trigo & J. Fernández.

Shell: Fragile & transparent. It presents an elongated and narrow last whorl, with an oval aperture and a short spire. Shell very similar to species of other native *Succinea* species, but with a marked microsculpture, forming a very fine reticulum easily observed under magnification (MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ, 2013).

Animal: Dark greyish-brown with white spots randomly distributed throughout its body.

Known distribution: A freshwater gastropod species native to North America that has spread widely throughout the world with records from Puerto Rico, Venezuela, Brazil, Argentina, Uruguay, Ecuador, Paraguay, Colombia, Peru, Australia, South Africa, Pacific Islands, Switzerland, Austria, Hungary, Greece, Czech Republic, Latvia and France (FECHTER & FALKNER, 1993; CORDEIRO & BOGAN, 2012; MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ, 2013; MARTÍN ÁLVAREZ, QUIÑONERO SALGADO & LÓPEZ SORIANO, 2016). In the Iberian Peninsula, it has been recorded in Barcelona, O Porriño (Pontevedra), Huelva, Benalmádena, Málaga and in Portugal, in Vouga and Mondego Rivers (MARTÍN ÁLVAREZ *ET AL.*, 2016; CASALS & SÁNCHEZ GONZÁLEZ, 2020).

Ecology: The habitat reported for this species is slow-flowing waters with typical freshwater vegetation, although it is also reported to tolerate brackish waters or at least with some tidal influ-

ence (MARTÍN ÁLVAREZ *ET AL.*, 2016). In our case, the sampled areas correspond to river sections where tides do not exert their influence and, therefore, are fresh waters. In both, Miñor and Muíños rivers, samplings were carried out in areas with moderately strong currents. The specimens were found among the riverside vegetation, with plant species like the exotic South American *Egeria densa* Planch, 1849 or the autochthonous *Sparganium emersum* Rehm, 1872.

Pseudosuccinea columella can be host of the trematode flatworm *Fasciola hepatica* (Linnaeus, 1758) whose life cycle develops in two hosts: a freshwater gastropod and a land mammal, causing the parasitic disease fascioliasis, one of the main diseases affecting domestic ruminants in the world. *Pseudosuccinea columella* has been confirmed as intermediate host of *F. hepatica* in Egypt, New Zealand, Brazil, Argentina, France, Dominican Republic, Guatemala and Cuba (LEPE LÓPEZ *ET AL.*, 2020).

Remarks: In October 2023, a sampling was carried out searching for exotic freshwater molluscs in Muíños River in the area of América beach, municipality of Nigrán, Pontevedra, where, by chance, some specimens were collected. In October 2024, a second sampling was carried out in another nearby river, Miñor, finding more specimens of this species.

The pathway of entry in Galicia is related to aquariology, since it is a

common species in freshwater aquariums.

In Galicia it had only been reported previously in Gándaras de Budiño. This is a wetland located in the municipality of O Porriño, in the province of Pontevedra,

so this is the second record for Galicia and the confirmation of its distribution outside artificial aquatic environments (CASALS & SÁNCHEZ GONZÁLEZ, 2020), where it is usual to find worldwide where this species has been introduced.

Family PLANORBIDAE

Menetus dilatatus (Gould, 1841) (Fig. 5C, D)

Material examined: GALICIA • 4 specimens; Pontevedra, Nigrán, Muíños River; 42°08'00.57"N, 08°48'39.84"W; 3 Oct. 2023; J.E. Trigo, L. Rodríguez and F. Febrero leg. • 12 specimens; Same data as for preceding; 30 Sep. 2024; J.E. Trigo and J. Fernández leg. • 2 specimens; Pontevedra, Baiona, Miñor River; 42°06'39.89"N, 08°46'17.08"W; 30 Sep. 2024.

Shell: Shells of this species are small (2-4 mm in width, less than 1 mm in height), characterized by yellowish green colour, and surface wrinkled by the growth lines. They usually have 2.5 - 3 whorls, separated by a well-defined suture. Last whorl has a sharp margin, and it rapidly enlarges, with the lip expanded, conferring the shell its trumpet-like shape.

Animal: Greyish colour with very small whitish dots randomly distributed all over the body. Black eyes located at the inner base of the tentacles, which at their base are transparent with a pinkish hue. They become darker in colour towards the ends.

Known distribution: It is a freshwater gastropod native to the eastern United States, from Florida and Texas to Maine. It was introduced in Europe, specifically in Great Britain, in the 19th century. From there it has spread to other European countries such as France, Germany, Poland, Czech Republic and

Portugal (QUINONERO SALGADO & LÓPEZ SORIANO, 2022).

Ecology: The specimens were found under the leaves of plants in contact with water, on the banks of the rivers sampled.

Remarks: As for the previous species, in October 2023 a sampling was carried out in Muíños River in the area of América Beach, municipality of Nigrán, Pontevedra. Among the molluscs found in the vegetation along the edges, three specimens of this small gastropod appeared.

In October 2024, sampling was repeated in the same river and in the Miñor River, in the municipality of Baiona, Pontevedra. In both rivers, several live specimens of *M. dilatatus* were found.

The pathway of entry of this species into Galicia, like the previous species, is related to aquariology, as it is also a common species in the freshwater aquariums of those involved in this hobby. This is the second record for Spain and the first for Galicia.

(Right page) Figure 5. Freshwater species. A: *Pseudosuccinea columella*, specimen from Muíños River and detail of its shell; B: *Pseudosuccinea columella*, living animal; C: *Menetus dilatatus*, living animal; D: *Menetus dilatatus*, specimens from Miñor River, Baiona, Pontevedra; E-G: *Ferrissia californica*. Specimens from Muíños River, Nigrán, Pontevedra.

Figura 5. Especies de agua dulce. A: Pseudosuccinea columella, ejemplar del río Muíños y detalle de su concha; B: Pseudosuccinea columella, animal vivo; C: Menetus dilatatus, animal vivo; D: Menetus dilatatus, ejemplares del río Miñor, Baiona, Pontevedra; E-G: Ferrissia californica, ejemplares del río Muíños Nigrán, Pontevedra.

Ferrissia californica (Rowell, 1863) (Fig. 5E, F)

Material examined: GALICIA • 4 specimens; Pontevedra, Nigrán, Muños River; 42°08'00.57"N, 08°48'39.84"W; 3 Oct. 2023; J.E. Trigo, L. Rodríguez and F. Febrero leg. • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, Baiona, Miñor River; 42°06'39.89"N, 08°46'17.08"W; 30 Sep. 2024; J.E. Trigo and J. Fernández leg.

Shell: Tiny limpet appearance. Very small, oval and transparent. Apex flattened and displaced to the right and towards the back.

Animal: Faded whitish colouration, almost transparent.

Known distribution: Freshwater gastropod native to North America, that has spread to Europe, Asia, South America, Africa and Oceania, and more specifically to countries such as the Czech Republic, Bulgaria, Austria, Spain, Moldova, Germany, The Netherlands, Poland, Slovakia, Great Britain, Portugal, Algeria, Tunisia, Morocco, Japan and Brazil (MABROUKI, GLÖER & FOUZI, 2023). This species has been reported in different places of the Iberian Peninsula such as Alicante, Barcelona, Girona, Navarra, Tarragona, Valencia, Castilla La Mancha and Madrid, as well as in the south and centre of Portugal (HOLYOAK, HOLYOAK & DA COSTA MENDES, 2019; CASALS & SÁNCHEZ GONZÁLEZ, 2020). In Galicia there is only one record of this species in Encoro do Con, in the municipality of Vilagarcía de Arousa, Pontevedra (GONZÁLEZ & COBO, 2006).

Ecology: In our samplings, it was found under permanently submerged riverside plant leaves.

Remarks: This species, due to its tiny size, goes easily unnoticed. In 2020, numerous empty shells were found in the substrate collected very few metres depth in front of the Muños River mouth, in the area of América beach, municipality of Nigrán, Pontevedra.

In October 2023, in a sampling carried out to locate freshwater exotic species, only two shells were collected. As aforementioned, the tiny size of this species makes it very easily unnoticeable.

In October 2024, a new sampling in the same river was done, and another two live specimens were found. In a subsequent sampling, it was not possible to find any specimens of this species.

In this case, the pathway of entry of this species is directly linked to aquariology, since the finding of other exotic species of gastropods and even aquatic plants used for this type of hobby in the same river provide obvious evidence.

This is the second record for Galicia and the confirmation of the existence of stable populations in our region.

Family SUCCINEIDAE

Succinea costaricana E. von Martens, 1898 (Fig. 6)

Material examined: GALICIA • 37 specimens; A Coruña, Oleiros, Dorneda, San Martiño; 4 Aug. 2023; J.E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Brión, Alqueidón, Agro Novo; 42°51'01.79"N, 08°40'44.85"W; 17 May 2024; J.E. Trigo leg.

Shell: Very thin and transparent with 3-4 whorls, the last of which is very large and occupies almost its entire size. Very marked suture.

Animal: Very dark colour, almost black, with short cephalic tentacles.

Known distribution: It is a species whose natural range extends from

(Right page) Figure 6. *Succinea costaricana*. A, B: specimens from Oleiros, A Coruña; C: living specimen from Brión.

(Página derecha) Figura 6. *Succinea costaricana*. A, B: ejemplares de Oleiros, A Coruña; C: ejemplar vivo de Brión.

México to Costa Rica. In the Iberian Peninsula, it has been recorded in Málaga, Barcelona, Tarragona and in two localities in Portugal: Leiria and Porto de Mós (HOLYOAK *ET AL.*, 2013). On the website biodiversidadvirtual.org, there are numerous entries of what may be specimens of this species referring to the provinces of Barcelona, Alicante, Murcia, Málaga, Cádiz, Jaén, Ciudad Real and Toledo, so it may be sufficiently established within the Iberian Peninsula to continue spreading and becoming impossible to eradicate.

Ecology: Is associated with moist microhabitats. In its natural range, it can reach a density of almost 300,000 specimens/ha, although this is a calculation on a value and, surely, lower than the real one; isolated animals were able to reproduce without mating and sometimes they are carriers of diseases or intermediate hosts of parasites (VILLALOBOS *ET AL.*, 1995). The potential, therefore, as a species of concern because of its capabilities, is enormous and it should be carefully monitored where it was found.

Remarks: In Spain, the first findings of this species in the provinces of Málaga and Barcelona caused confusion, because the morphologically similar native species of the genera *Succinea* and *Oxyloma* are basically hygrophilous, i.e. typical of permanently humid places such as ditches, ponds or banks of springs and streams, with herbaceous vegetation, aquatic plants, stones and damp soil (ONDINA, HERMIDA & OUTEIRO, 1996), whereas the alien species was found in terrestrial areas without nearby springs, ponds or streams.

In Galicia, a large population was found in August 2023. A total of 37 live specimens were collected, ranging in size from 2 to 6 mm, while a further 20 were observed at inaccessible heights, attached to the outside wall of a private house in Santa Cruz, in the municipality of Oleiros, A Coruña. This wall, at an angle, facing south and west and enclosed by grass and decorative white stone, was the place chosen by all the specimens as the most suitable, as no others were found on the other exterior walls of the house. The site of the finding is a private estate, closed to the public and with the nearest stream some 200 m away with a road in between. This detail was the one that attracted most the attention and would help largely in its later identification.

In May 2024, a live specimen was found among the ornamental plants of a private house in the municipality of Brión, A Coruña. In this case, it was an adult specimen. It is very possible that it could have arrived through ornamental plants purchased shortly before in plant nurseries in Vigo.

As with the previous species, the pathway of entry into the area is the ornamental plant trade. This type of trade is causing this species to spread very quickly and easily throughout Galicia, with the additional danger of dispersing entry points for this species, which could become invasive if left unchecked.

It is possible that several species are hidden under this taxon (VILLALOBOS *ET AL.*, 1995). Photographs observed in various sources based on citizen science reveal differences in animal colours and shell shapes, as well as sizes.

This is the first record for Galicia.

Class BIVALVIA
Order ARCIDA
Family ARCIDAE

Anadara kagoshimensis (Tokunaga, 1906) (Fig. 7A)

Material examined: GALICIA • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Miño, Alameda Beach; 43°20'22.58"N, 8°12'16.18"W; 8 Feb. 2015; A. Trincado leg. • 1 valve; A Coruña, Muros, Esteiro Beach; 42°47'28.30"N, 8°58'36.33"W; J.E. Trigo leg.

Shell: Subquadrangular, oval, equivalent, robust and very globose. Anterior margin obliquely truncated. Ventral margin slightly curved, almost straight and strongly serrate. Sculpture of about 30 strongly marked radial ribs. Periostracum fibrous, dark brown and very close fitting. Whitish to very light brown colouration.

Known distribution: A species from the northwestern Pacific Ocean that has first spread to the Mediterranean, Black Sea and Sea of Azov and particularly to the Adriatic (STRAPELLA ET AL., 2017; TRIGO ET AL., 2018). On the Atlantic coasts of the Iberian Peninsula, this species has only been reported in Galicia, at first erroneously as *Scapharca cornea* (Reeve, 1844) (ROLÁN ET AL., 1985), and later as *A. kagoshimensis* (TRIGO ET AL., 2018).

Remarks: This species has so far only been recorded in the Ria of Arousa, where it has been found from O Grove to the town of Rianxo, located on the northern coast. The appearance of a live specimen in the Ria of Betanzos (Rías Altas), very close to the city of A Coruña, but very far from the Ria of Arousa (Rías Baixas), is worrying, since it increases its range and, therefore, the area occupied as a possible invader. From there, the threat of being a possible new focus of dissemination to other nearby rias within the Ártabro Gulf like A Coruña, Ares and Ferrol and other adjacent areas, is very great (BAÑÓN ET AL., 2015). Taking into account that the finding dates back to 2015, it is possible that more sites are affected in that area, which commands further sampling to clarify the real situation.

The pathway for the entry of this species into the Ria of Betanzos has been the culture of different species of clam. Consultations with the technical assistance of the Miño Fishermen's Union have confirmed that prior to 2010, seed of different clam species was purchased from Chioggia, Italy, where *A. kagoshimensis* maintains large populations. It is not surprising, therefore, that among the seed purchased there may have been juveniles of this species which were able to survive and develop in favourable conditions in this estuary. Based on the bibliographic data consulted, specifically in the Black Sea, a size of 60 mm is equivalent to an age of between 4 and 5 years (DAĞTEKIN ET AL., 2023) and in the Sea of Azov, it is estimated that an average length of 50 mm is reached at 5-6 years (MIRZOEVA & ZHUKOV, 2021). It is therefore perfectly feasible that a 60 mm specimen could have arrived before 2010 in the Ria de Betanzos and developed without incident.

Between its initial appearance in 1983 (ROLÁN ET AL., 1985, as *Scapharca cornea*) in Noalla, Sanxenxo, only two empty shells were found in intermediate points of the *ría*, but in 2013, shellfish gatherers from Carril, Vilagarcía de Arousa, collected a total of 236 specimens (BAÑÓN ET AL., 2015). Although a single valve was recently found in the Ria de Muros, we will wait for more data to confirm its presence at this point. In Galicia, this species has so far only been recorded in the Ria de Arousa and in its new area of expansion Ria de Betanzos.

Anadara transversa (Say, 1822) (Fig. 7B)

Material examined: GALICIA • 16 specimens; Pontevedra, Sanxenxo, Noalla; 42°26'59.30"N, 8°51'39.55"W; 8 Jun. 2010; Juan E. Trigo leg. • 10 specimens; Same data as for preceding; 23 Nov. 2010; Juan E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, Cambados, Tragove; 42°31'17.62"N, 8°49'40.30"W; 5 Jun. 2023; Patricia Rúa leg.

Shell: Solid, inequivalve, inequilateral. Sculpture of radial ribs. Right valve larger than the left valve. Internal ventral margin strongly crenulate. Periostracum dark brown. Shell whitish to cream.

Known distribution: Its natural range includes part of the east coast of the United States, from Massachusetts to Florida and Texas (ABBOTT, 1974). From there, it has spread across the Mediter-

ranean, from Turkey (DEMIR, 1977) to the Adriatic Sea (DESPALATOVIĆ ET AL., 2013), the western Mediterranean (LÓPEZ SORIANO, 2011) and to the European Atlantic (TRIGO ET AL., 2018).

Remarks: This species was first misidentified (DEMIR, 1977) as *Arca amygdalum* Philippi, 1847 from the Indo-Pacific (China) and later renamed *Anadara demiri* (Piani, 1981). Molecular analyses were later carried out and it was concluded that it is indeed the American species *A. transversa* (ALBANO ET AL., 2009).

The behaviour of this species tends to be invasive and it is included among the top 100 worst invasive species threatening biodiversity in Europe (STREFTARIS & ZENETOS, 2006), so it will be necessary to monitor very closely its possible proliferation in the Ría de Arousa.

The first 26 specimens found in Galicia were in Noalla, Sanxenxo, Pontevedra in 2010. The specimen found in Tragove, Cambados dates back to 2023 what indicates that its range in the Ría de Arousa is expanding and the presence of this species in this *ría* is therefore, confirmed.

Order LUCINIDA
Family LUCINIDAE
Subfamily LEUCOSPHAERINAE

Loripinus cf senegalensis (Cosel, 2005) (Fig. 8)

Material examined: GALICIA • 2 valves; A Coruña, Corme; 43°15'46.15"N, 8°57'55.50"W; 31 Dec. 2002; J. E. Trigo leg. • 1 valve; A Coruña, Camelle; 43°11'05.98"N, 9°05'25.73"W; 30 Apr. 1999; J. E. Trigo leg. • 1 valve; A Coruña, Muros; 42°46'33.43"N, 9°03'22.81"W; 22 Jan. 1999; J. E. Trigo leg. • 5 valves; A Coruña; 43°21'06.94"N, 8°23'02.71"W; 5 Jan. 2003; J. E. Trigo leg. • 1 valve; A Coruña, Miño, Alameda Beach. 43°21'04.62"N, 8°12'52.52"W; A. Trincado leg.

Shell: Fragile in appearance, although solid. Rounded profile and globular shape. Sculpture formed by numerous and very fine concentric lines. Whitish inside and yellowish-brown outside.

Known distribution: From Mauritania to Senegal (TAYLOR & GLOVER, 2005; COSEL & GOFAS, 2019).

Ecology: The substrate on which possible live specimens could settle and the depth of the water column at which they could be found, as well as the depth of burial, are unknown, so finding whole specimens from which viable samples could be obtained for molecular analysis has not been possible.

Remarks: Initially, the shells found in different parts of Galicia were identified as *Anodontia fragilis* (R. A. Philippi, 1836), noting that the sizes of the shells found were exceptional, as the smallest was 16 mm (ANADÓN & ORTEA, 1978; ROLÁN ET AL., 1999; ROLÁN & TRIGO, 2002, 2003), while HIDALGO (1917) men-

tions 14 mm and PARENZAN (1976) 13 mm. It was thought that it could be this species because it was the closest that could be found in European waters. It was later found not to be this one and it was reidentified as *Anodontia* sp (TRIGO ET AL., 2018).

There are similar African species (COSEL & GOFAS, 2019) such as *Loripinus subfragilis* (Dautzenberg, 1910), whose range is from Mauritania to southern Angola, *Bythosphaera subrostrata* (Cosel, 1989), from Cameroon to Angola, *Afrophysema chevalieri* (Cosel, 2005), from Ivory Coast to Gabon and *Loripinus senegalensis* (Cosel, 2005), from Mauritania to Senegal.

Of the five previous species, *B. subrostrata*, *L. subfragilis* and *L. fragilis* do not coincide with the Galician shells, as none of them are longer than 16 mm, while those found in Galicia start at 16 mm and reach a maximum length of 38.5 mm. However, the species *L. fragilis*, with a Mediterranean distribution, was considered first, as it is the closest species that

Figure 7. A: *Anadara kagoshimensis*, specimen from Alameda beach, Miño, A Coruña; B: *Anadara transversa*, Tragove, Cambados, Pontevedra; C: *Mya arenaria*, specimen found in Ares, A Coruña.
Figura 7. A: *Anadara kagoshimensis*, ejemplar de la playa de la Alameda. Miño, A Coruña; B: *Anadara transversa*, Tragove, Cambados, Pontevedra; C: *Mya arenaria*, ejemplar encontrado en Ares, A Coruña.

can be found in European waters. There are many other species that reach a larger size in Atlantic waters than in the Mediterranean, either due to nutritional, physical, chemical or a mixture of all of these factors and that is why it was not ruled out from the beginning.

In terms of size, only *A. chevalieri* and *L. senegalensis* can be considered. The morphological characters of the shell profile tend to be somewhat variable, but the muscular impressions and even the pallial line between species is usually a very specific distinctive character, as mentioned above. By making a visual comparison of these two African species and the shells obtained in Galicia, which coincide in muscle impressions, it was finally concluded that the shells found in our waters correspond to *L. senegalensis*.

On the other hand, there are very few published data on the occurrence of *Loripinus* in the Mediterranean area or on the Atlantic coast of the Iberian Peninsula. One of them (Anadón & Ortea, 1978) cites *Loripinus fragilis* in the localities of Baiona (Pontevedra), O Barqueiro (A Coruña) and Colunga (Asturias). Although the work refers to three valves found in each of the aforementioned localities, it only provides measurements of that from Baiona, specifically, 32 × 29 mm. Although it is indicated that the size is much larger than those reported by various authors, no further details are given on this

issue, which is reflected as a simple anecdote, and it is only indicated that there are no other reports of *L. fragilis* above the 38°N parallel (i.e. southern Portugal), and therefore it is a range extension. A photograph of the shell is included, of which dimensions and morphological characteristics fit perfectly the specimens found between Costa da Morte and the Ártabro Gulf. Of the other two valves mentioned in the aforementioned work, we have only been able to find a reference (as *L. fragilis*) to that one found in Colunga in the eastern part of Asturias, in the unpublished doctoral thesis of Jesús Ortea (1977), where the author states dimensions of 13.3 × 15.5 mm. He does not comment on the size of the shell, which is slightly larger than the records for this species, although he does comment on its colouring, which he describes as white, and on its state of preservation, which the author considered good. Given its size, it could very well be indeed *L. fragilis*, but no other shells or specimens have been found in the Cantabrian Sea, so the question remains as to whether it could be a juvenile specimen of *L. senegalensis*. Of the shell found in O Barqueiro, there is no reference to size or state of conservation, and there are no drawings or photographs.

Assuming that the Galician records correspond to the species *L. senegalensis*, this is the first record for Europe, the Iberian Peninsula and Galicia.

(Right page) Figure 8. A-E. Valves of *Loripinus cf senegalensis*. A: Corme, two valves, H= 19, W= 21mm; H= 29, W= 33 mm; B: Camelle, one valve, H= 18, W= 20 mm; C: Muros, one valve, H= 28, W= 31 mm; D: Ares, one valve, H= 34, W=38.5 mm; E: A Coruña, five valves, H=20, W= 23; H= 20, W= 22; H= 21, W= 23; H= 16, W= 17; H= 17; W= 19 mm. F: *Loripinus fragilis*, Cullera, Valencia, H= 8, W= 9mm; G: comparison of muscle scars between *Loripinus senegalensis*, valves found in Galicia and *Loripinus fragilis* (drawings by R. von Cosel, reproduced from TAYLOR & GLOVER, 2005).

(Página derecha) Figura 8. A-E. Valvas de *Loripinus cf senegalensis*. A: Corme, dos valvas, H= 19, W= 21mm; H= 29, W= 33 mm; B: Camelle, una valva, H= 18, W= 20 mm; C: Muros, una valva, H= 28, W= 31 mm; D: Ares, una valva, H= 34, W=38.5 mm; E: A Coruña, cinco valvas, H=20, W= 23; H= 20, W= 22; H= 21, W= 23; H= 16, W= 17; H= 17; W= 19 mm; F: *Loripinus fragilis*, Cullera, Valencia. H= 8, W= 9mm; G: comparación de las huellas musculares de *Loripinus senegalensis*, valvas encontradas en Galicia y *Loripinus fragilis* (dibujos de R. von Cosel, reproducidos de TAYLOR & GLOVER, 2005).

G

Loripinus senegalensis

Galicia

Loripinus fragilis

Order MYIDA
Family MYIDAE

Mya arenaria Linnaeus, 1758 (Fig. 7C)

Material examined: GALICIA • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Ares, Ares Beach; 43°25'44.52"N, 8°14'18.65"W; M. Suárez leg.

Shell: Solid, slightly inequivalve and almost equilateral. Oval profile, rounded anteriorly and angular posteriorly. Sculpture with well-marked and irregularly arranged growth lines. Smooth margin. Periostracum very thin, light brown. Whitish colouration. Left valve with a large, chondrophore, very conspicuous, spoon-shaped tooth.

Known distribution: Circumboreal species, native to the Arctic Ocean. In the Pacific, north coast of the United States and Canada, Alaska to California and Kamchatka to Japan (TEBBLE, 1966). In Europe, it is well established in the White Sea, Norway, the Swedish coast, the Baltic, the German coast, in estuaries of The Netherlands, Belgium, the British Islands, Ireland and the Atlantic coast of France. In the Mediterranean Sea, there are records in France, Italy, Greece and Turkey as well as in the Black Sea (STRASSER, 1999; CONDE ET AL., 2011). In the Iberian Peninsula, it specifically has been reported in Portugal (Hidalgo, 1917), Tagus estuary (CONDE, NOVAIS &

DOMÍNGUEZ, 2010), in the Lima estuary (CONDE ET AL., 2011) and in Gibraltar (HIDALGO, 1917). In Asturias, it has been cited in the Lloredo inlet, Avilés (RAVEN ET AL., 2022) based on two valves found in different occasions in that place. It is also cited on the Basque coast without specifying further data (BORJA & MUXIKA, 2001). In Galicia, it is known to occur in the Ría de Arousa (ROLÁN & ACUÑA, 2008; TRIGO ET AL., 2018).

Remarks: In little more than 15 years, this species has gone from only being found in Ría de Arousa to being detected from Arcade, in the Ría de Vigo, to the town of Ares, in the Ártabro Gulf.

As an exotic species, its area of expansion in Galician waters is constantly expanding, and more so than some other exotic species that have appeared previously. It can be compared to *Crepidula fornicata* or *Crepidipatella dilatata* in area of extension taken with respect to the time this species has been known to be in Galicia.

Family VENERIDAE

Mercenaria mercenaria (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 9)

Material examined: GALICIA • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Outes, Broña Beach; 42°48'07.05"N, 8°55'46.22"W; 3 Jan. 2021; O. Montero and L. Solís leg. • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, Vilagarcía de Arousa, Cortegada Island; 42°36'51.09"N, 8°47'15.42"W; 17 Jul. 2018; J. Fernández leg. • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, Vilanova de Arousa; 42°33'40.76"N, 8°49'45.86"W; J. Fernández leg. • 2 specimens; Pontevedra, Arousa Island, A Arnela; 42°31'20.82"N, 8°51'46.74"W; 6 Aug. 2020; J. Fernández leg. • 1 specimen; Same data as for preceding; 7 Aug. 2020; J. Fernández leg. • 1 specimen; Same data as for preceding; 14 Aug. 2020; J. Fernández leg. • 2 specimens; A Coruña, San Fiz, A Lama Beach; 43°43'18.69"N, 7°42'06.55"W; Jan. 2017; G. del Río leg.

Shell: Thick shell, usually triangular, light brown to grey in colour. Concentric and variable growth lines on the shell. Shiny interior of the shell, white or with purple or bluish spots of irregular size.

Ecology: The ideal habitat of *M. mercenaria* in its natural distribution range is sandy seabeds ranging from the intertidal zone to a depth of 15 m. The distribution of natural populations is influ-

Figure 9. A: *Mercenaria mercenaria*. Specimens (68 × 58 mm, 71 × 59 mm, 84 × 71 mm, 84 × 69 mm, 78 × 70 mm) found on Ría de Arousa, Cortegada Island, Vilagarcía de Arousa, Pontevedra; B: specimen (50 × 43 mm) from Arousa Island, Pontevedra; C: specimen (92 × 85 mm) from Ría de Muros, Outes, A Coruña; D: detail of the hinge.

Figura 9. A: *Mercenaria mercenaria*. Ejemplares (68 × 58 mm, 71 × 59 mm, 84 × 71 mm, 84 × 69 mm, 78 × 70 mm) encontrados en la Ría de Arousa, isla de Cortegada, Vilagarcía de Arousa, Pontevedra; B: ejemplar (50 × 43 mm) de Illa de Arousa, Pontevedra; C: ejemplar (92 × 85 mm) de Ría de Muros, Outes, A Coruña; D: detalle de la charnela.

enced by the texture of the sediment, with higher densities on sandy bottoms and lower on muddy ones (WELLS, 1957). In our case, all the specimens have been collected on sandy substrate between the high intertidal level and 3 m depth. Taking into account the growth ratios of this species (EVERSOLE, GRIMES & ELDRIDGE, 1986), the largest of the specimens obtained, measuring 93 mm, could be over 8 years old. The smallest, measuring 64 mm, could be around 5 years old, which leads to the belief that there are stable populations of this species in our waters with a significant geographical range within Galicia.

Known distribution: The native geographic distribution of *M. mercenaria* ranges from the Gulf of St. Lawrence in Canada through the northern Gulf of Mexico to Texas (ABBOTT, 1974). Due to its commercial interest, it has been introduced to the west coast of the United States (Washington and California). Outside the United States, it has been introduced to the Caribbean region in Puerto Rico; to the European Atlantic, in countries such as United Kingdom, France, the Netherlands, Belgium, and Italy (POPPE & GOTO, 1993; TUROLLA, 2006) and to Asia, Taiwan (FAO, 2009). Although its introduction into Europe as a species of commercial interest dates back to 1925 (MITCHEL, 1974), it was not until 2012 when it was first recorded in the Iberian Peninsula (ARIAS & ANADÓN, 2012) in the waters of the Cantabrian Sea.

Remarks: A total of nine live specimens have been obtained in different

samplings carried out in the Ría de Muros, Ría de Arousa and Ría de O Barqueiro between 2017 and 2020. Four of them were found in the shellfish bank of Arousa Island (Pontevedra) known as A Arnela, one in the Esteiro de Vilanova de Arousa and one more collected in a park near the Cortegada Island. In this last case, this specimen was part of a larger batch detected in the fish auction of Carril, Pontevedra, but it is not possible to specify what happened to them, although they were most certainly put up for sale under the name of another species. One more specimen, also alive, was found in Ría de Muros, in the town of Outes, A Coruña, and two more, also alive, in the town of O Barqueiro, A Coruña, in 2017 and 2019. In addition, biologists from Xunta de Galicia have reported the discovery of more specimens in the Ría de Vigo, although they were not collected.

The data obtained indicate that juveniles of this species may have arrived mixed with seed from different species of clam that are usually brought for cultivation from France, Italy or the United Kingdom, countries in which *M. mercenaria* has already been introduced for commercial purposes for years (TUROLLA, 2006). Another hypothesis for its introduction into Galicia may be experimental cultures of this species that began in the 1980s in the town of Vilagarcía de Arousa (Troncoso, pers. comm.), but we have no official data on this matter.

This record is the first for Galicia and a confirmation of its occurrence in the northern part of the Iberian Peninsula.

DISCUSSION

In this work a total of 11 species are studied, 6 gastropods and 5 bivalves. As far as gastropods are concerned, our material of *Ocenebrellus inornatus* constitutes the first record for Spanish waters. *Succinea costaricana* is the first record for Galicia, and *Menetus dilatatus* is the second record for Spain and the first record for Galicia. For the remaining species, new data are provided, which

are considered interesting. Regarding the bivalves, *Loripinus* cf. *senegalensis* would be the first record for Europe. *Mercenaria mercenaria* is the first record for Galicia and the second for Spain, but the first one with evidence for established populations.

The arrival of exotic marine species of molluscs at Galicia has been increasing since the 80's of the 20th century.

Virtually all of them have settled in our waters due to the activities related to aquaculture, and new other keep arising, as it is the case of those studied in the present work. Their settlement and subsequent development in all cases are favoured from the conditions in Galician *rías*: plenty of food due to the oceanic upwelling loaded with nutrients and sheltered areas protected from the weather in winter and warmer temperatures in summer, which, unfortunately, keep increasing every year.

Most of the species that have appeared so far do not seem to affect native species and apparently coexist in perfect harmony. However, a minority seriously affect them, either because they are carnivorous species that feed on native bivalves of Galician waters and even on some exotic species such as *Ruditapes philippinarum* (Adams & Reeve, 1850), or because they displace them, causing their disappearance from their natural habitats. Sadly, their effects are becoming more noticeable every year.

Regarding *O. inornatus*, after having been detected in Arousa Island, the authors immediately cautioned against the danger of this species for commercial bivalves in the local Fishermen's Union. In campaigns regularly carried out since 2020, a great number of specimens has been removed from the grounds in order to reduce the demographic pressure of this species and to avoid losses in the farming of bivalves of the families *Veneridae* and *Cardiidae*, typical of this *ría*. Others, such as *Crepidatella dilatata*, have spread very rapidly throughout the four *Rías Baixas* and certain areas are completely covered by this species, displacing native species entirely. Its behaviour is highly invasive, so it is considered that it should be added to the Spanish list of invasive species without further delay. Definitely, each alien species needs of a determined and exclusive action, which differs from that of others, to keep their populations controlled or even achieve their complete eradication, since every species acts and behaves in a certain way.

Other less aggressive species, for the moment, are the bivalves *Anadara*

kagoshimensis and *Anadara transversa*. The former has already appeared outside *Ría de Arousa*, where it had been confined until now, in two different locations: *Ría de Muros* and *Ría de Ares* in the *Ártabro Gulf*. The second is observed to be expanding in *Ría de Arousa*. The densities that both species can reach are so high that they do not allow other bivalve species to develop in their environment, which should raise great concern about their expansion in Galician waters.

The concern in Europe is evident and the losses caused by exotic and invasive species are estimated in 12,000 million euros per year (EUROPEAN UNION, 2024). However, there is something going wrong at the moment that, at least in Galicia, no action is taken in order to control, tackle or eradicate the expansion of those which have emerged and those likely to arrive onto our coasts.

It is necessary for the competent public administrations to implement effective management measures against the most harmful invasive alien species, in coordination with the Fishermen's Unions and other stakeholders. Specifically, there is a need for the implementation of control and eradication programmes, in accordance with the provisions of Spanish laws (RD 630/2013, of 2 August), which regulates the Spanish Catalogue of Invasive Alien Species. The legislation in force in this area should be strictly applied, by cataloguing as invasive alien species all those that meet the stipulated legal requirements so that they can be managed appropriately, without inaction and without favouring their commercial exploitation, as it is the case with the species *Crepidula fornicata* and *Crepidatella dilatata*. The latter species is not included in the catalogue and should have been so for years due to the very clear invasive behaviour observed at different points along the coasts of Galicia. In many areas where it has naturalised, it has ended up displacing all the marine invertebrate species that were previously found in the occupied areas.

It is also necessary to develop environmental awareness programmes in these invasive alien species aimed at different productive sectors and social groups, as well as to differentiate these non-native species (e.g. *Ocenebrellus inornatus*) from the more similar autochthonous species (e.g. *Ocenebra erinaceus*).

Public authorities must therefore act with precision and the best available scientific knowledge. This, apart from ensuring the effectiveness of management, control and eradication measures using economic resources efficiently, must also include assessing the cost savings from adopting early warning and constant monitoring measures, as opposed to the millions of euros in losses caused by uncontrolled invasive alien species.

The monitoring of alien species is a complex task that requires enormous effort, both in terms of time, resources and the updating of information. Increasingly extensive samplings are carried out, not only in marine environments, but also on land and in freshwater. They are detected, some very early, correctly identified -sometimes after investing a lot of time-, and the corresponding warning is sent to the authorities, who seem to care very little in an area like Galicia, one of the world's leading powers in the exploitation of commercial bivalves. Species continue to arrive from all over the world and some of those that have already established themselves are causing very serious ecological problems and are already creating economic issues.

This work serves as a warning and a call to attention about what should be considered: four alien species not registered until now in Galicia in the marine, terrestrial and freshwater environments: *Ocenebrellus inornatus*, *Succinea costaricana*, *Menetus dilatatus* and *Mercenaria mercenaria*. The confirmation of the existence of two other freshwater species: *Ferrissia californica* and *Pseudosuccinea columella*, the latter being a possible host of parasites that transmit livestock diseases and other potentially dangerous ones for humans. Additionally, as previ-

ously mentioned, another species treated in this work, *Crepidatella dilatata*, should be classified as invasive.

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